

Avifaunal assemblage in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

A positive relationship between avifaunal distribution and vegetation may be interrupted by habitat disturbances as environmental stresses. Hence, general pattern of avifaunal distribution across elevational gradients was qualitatively characterized. Vegetation ranging from lowland, montane and mossy forest was explored for bird utilization. A combination of participatory line-transect survey and mist-netting technique were used to sample bird species in eight sampling sites in Mt. Hamiguitan Range from July 2006 to March 2007. There were a cumulative of 53 species of birds assigned to 26 families and 11 orders. Twenty species (37.8%) of which are Philippine endemics and 10 species (18.9%) are confined in Mindanao. With the altitudinal isolation of vegetation, the number of species, abundance and endemism increase as elevation decreases. Hence, there is a direct relationship between vegetation and niche breadth of birds. Thus, the higher affinity of the location of vegetation, the greater number of similar species occurred between them. Species of birds are highly similar between proximate habitats like lowland dipterocarp forest and montane forest as well as montane and mossy forest than in vegetation with greater elevational gradient. Therefore, communities of birds with reference to diversity, abundance and endemism are distributed based on vegetation at increasing elevation in a tropical rainforest.

Key words: avifauna, biodiversity, elevation, endemic species, vegetation

INTRODUCTION

Bird species make up the most diverse class of terrestrial vertebrates in the world. In tropical countries like the Philippines, birds are also highly diverse with 576 known species, of which 325 are geographically restricted in Mindanao (Kennedy *et al.* 2000). However, 86 species of bird are classified between vulnerable to extinct in the wild in the past surveys (Oliver and Heaney 1996) which may be brought about by loss of habitat, hunting and forest land use conversion and climb up if these anthropogenic activities would continue. Out of these numbers, 45 species of threatened birds are endemic or geographically restricted in the country (Oliver and Heaney 1996). The proportion of large forest cover decreased dramatically as population and demand of resources increase which is also the same concern arising from different regions in the world. Unfortunately, Mt. Hamiguitan (1,620 masl) in eastern Mindanao belongs to this explored

sites for mining, hunting and logging due to high amounts of valuable mineral deposits, rich wildlife and timber trees. Utilization of these resources may create conflict with the wide variety of the endemic and threatened bird species in a tropical forest. These basic needs of bird survival which are likely more affected with these habitat nuisances include their foraging and roosting sites from lowland to montane and mossy forest located in increasing altitude. Bird distribution in highly elevated montane forest in Greater Mindanao ecoregion overlaps with the Mindanao and the Eastern Visayas Endemic Bird Area (EBA). The EBA consists of 51 restricted-range species, 26 of which are montane and mossy forest bird specialists in this faunal region. All of the restricted-range birds are forest species. There are 24 endemic or near-endemic bird species recorded in the ecoregion (Kennedy *et al.* 2000) with fewer restricted range species in the lowland ecoregion

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(Stattersfield et al. 1998; Collar et al. 1999). However, a large portion of lowland dipterocarp forest holds a significant number of endemic birds too. Hence, there is a need to assess the species composition, diversity and endemism of birds at all levels of a mountain range with tropical forest whether they live in various habitats since they these species in a forest ecosystem serve as good biological indicators of its ecological state.

Basically, avifauna is terrestrial warm-blooded and oviparous vertebrate characterized by feathers for insulation, specialized wings and hollow bones for maneuvering. Most group of birds can fly with the exemption of ratites which are flightless and several others particularly endemic island species have lost this ability. They exhibited various feeding guilds which include nectar, plants, seeds, carrion, and other small animals because birds have developed various types of beaks based on their food preference. They have a high rate of metabolism corresponding to their high rate of food intake. Birds lay hard-shelled eggs as an adaptation to land. Majority of the bird species are diurnal or active during the day and their peak activity in the early morning is spend as foraging time however some birds such as owls and nightjars prefer to forage at night for insects and fruits and are referred to as nocturnal or crepuscular.

Moreover, birds are among the most extensively studied of all animal groups. Though

studied well, bird composition in an ascending elevational pattern and forest cover in the remaining pristine tropical forest is vital for establishing conservation actions and further monitoring on the status of the forest ecosystem. Thus, this study aimed at investigating the pattern of bird distribution in terms of vertical stratification, feeding guilds, endemism and diversity in vegetation located in increasing elevation of a tropical forest.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Habitat Characterization

Mt. Hamiguitan Wildlife Sanctuary is situated in eastern Mindanao at the southeastern part of the Philippine archipelago (**Figure 1**). It is peculiar because it possesses bonsai trees situated from the lowland to the summit of the mountain range. Three types of habitat are classified such as lowland dipterocarp forest, montane forest and mossy dipterocarp forest. Lowland dipterocarp forest lies between $06^{\circ} 46' 22''$ N and $126^{\circ} 08' 49''$ E in Mt. Hamiguitan. This area is mostly covered by lower dipterocarp (75 to 370 masl) and upper dipterocarp forest (75 to 370 masl). *Gleichenia*, *Hoya*, *Falcatifolium* and *Agamaila* were attached commensally to tall and large dipterocarp trees. Rattan and *Cyathea frutescens* and *Medinella* composed the understorey plants. Pandan, *Freycinetia* and *Nepenthes* were also common in this forest. Leaf litter and humus cover were

Figure 1. Maps of the Philippines (a.), Mindanao (b.), Eastern Mindanao (c.) and Mt. Hamiguitan (d.) study area.

abundant in the site. The area is slightly sloping (15° to 40°). The height of emergent trees (*Agathis philippensis*) reached 50 to 70 m with a dbh (diameter at breast height) of 50.8 to 76.2 cm. Canopy trees (*Shorea contorta* and *Shorea polysperma*) are around 40 to 50 m tall with a dbh of 25.4 cm. Waterfalls and active springs were also found in the site. Anthropological clearing for farming of the residents near the site was about 30 to 500 m away from the forest. Visible activities such as drilling test for mining, mining road survey and logging were predominant within the sampling area.

On the other hand, montane forest vegetation is composed of the lower and upper montane forest. It is located at 371 to 715 masl with coordinates $06^{\circ} 43' 33''$ N and $126^{\circ} 09' 53''$ E. Pandan, *Ficus*, pitcher plants and moss were prominent in the site. Humus, leaf litter cover and exposed rocks were also abundant on the ground. The steepness of the site ranged from 20° to 85° . Emergent trees like *A. philippensis* and *Shorea contorta* were 60 to 70 m taller with a dbh of 2.5 cm to

1.5 m than canopy trees with a height of 50 m and dbh of 15.2 to 30.5 cm. Water outlets such as creeks, rivers, waterfalls and springs were situated within the study area. This site was far from anthropogenic activities unlike the lowland forest, however human encroachment was possible. Habitat disturbances included rattan gathering, mining, logging roads and trail. Moreover, mossy forest is found from the edge of the upper montane forest up to the summit of the mountain range at 716 to 1500 masl. Mosses were attached to tree trunks, logs and forest floor which make up most of the entire forest. Different species of pitcher plants were growing on trees while others on the ground and boulders. The thickness of leaf litter and humus is due to slow decomposition in higher elevation. Heights of bonsai trees found such as *Callophyllum blancoi*, *Leptospermum*, *Schefflera* and *A. philippensis* are around 3 m above the ground while the dipterocarp trees adjacent to bonsai trees were 30 to 50 m taller. River, streams and waterfalls were abundant in the sampling site. Human entry and helipad clearing within the mossy forest may affect the habitat.

Figure 2. Topographic map showing the location of the sampling sites in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines.

Avifaunal Assessment

Field sampling was conducted using both line-transect survey following existing trail and mist-netting method in vertical forest stratum in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao (**Figure 2**). Census was done from three to four days every month which began on July 2006 to March 2007 for seven consecutive months. Species-effort curve increases continuously from the start of the sampling period up to the end employing both methods. The list of birds per vegetation is limited by the unequal length of sampling in each habitat across elevational gradients.

Transect Walk Survey and Its Efficiency. Two-km line transect survey was conducted in selected eight sampling sites with different vegetative cover in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental. These were laid down in three identified types of habitat such as lowland dipterocarp forest, montane forest and mossy forest. Both elevation/altitude and coordinates were recorded using a hand-held Global Positioning System for each site. The transect line was divided into 20 points with an interval of 100 m. All birds seen and heard within the 20 m from both sides of the transect line were recorded by a local expert and a researcher from 0600-1600 hr. Birds heard and seen beyond 20 m from the transect line were also recorded as supplementary data. Vertical stratum of birds was also evaluated. Local researchers with close acquaintance of birds in the area were tapped in surveying birds along with researchers consisting of two groups. The first group did the survey in the morning from 0600-1000 hr while the second team took the inventory from 1200-1600 hr following the established line on the trail depending on the accessibility of the terrain. A minimum of 1 hr km^{-1} for a total of 2 hrs for 2 km were utilized for each site.

Mist-netting Method and Its Efficiency. Ten mist nets measuring 12 m long and 2.6 m high and 33-mm mesh-size were set in all sampling sites in Mt. Hamiguitan in three to four netting days per site. Mist nets were strategically placed in flyways, forest edge, foraging areas and forest interior in a vertical forest stratum on ground (1 to 5 m), middle canopy (5 to 10 m) and upper canopy

(10 to 15 m). Mist nets were left open from 0600 to 1700 hr to capture diurnal birds and 1700 to 0600 hr to collect nocturnal birds. All mist nets were checked twice in the morning, afternoon and evening. All birds captured were retrieved from the mist nets and were placed immediately in the net bags for recording and identification purposes. Stratum from where it was captured was noted in the collection data sheet. Captured birds were measured using a dial/vernier caliper. Morphometrics such as bill length (Bl), tarsus length (Tl), wing-cord (W) and total length (TL) were obtained from each bird. Age and sex of each species if possible were also noted. Modes of feeding of birds were also evaluated. Distinguishing morphological characteristics of each bird species were determined and compared to the descriptions of birds of *Kennedy et al. (2000)* in *A Guide to the Birds of the Philippines*. Captures were marked by clipping the outermost claw in the right toes before releasing them back to its natural habitat after identification. Voucher specimens of each species were preserved in 75% ethyl alcohol in the University of the Philippines Mindanao (UP Min) and Central Mindanao University (CMU) wildlife museums.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Species Composition of Birds

Both field techniques yielded a total of 53 bird species from lowland dipterocarp forest, montane forest to mossy forest in Mt. Hamiguitan. Although there was a biased sampling per vegetation, a general breakdown of 50 species for 291.5 man-hr with eight captures, 23 species for 110 man-hr without captures and 20 species for 88.6 man-hr with six species in lowland dipterocarp, montane and mossy forest, respectively, can be deduced using both techniques (**Table 1**). More evident bird species were recorded using transect-walk survey than minimal list using mist-netting method because of the cryptic behavior of these wild animals in a tropical forest. According to the previous studies near this region (*Silvosa et al. 2007; Caro 2008*), lowland and upper dipterocarp forest harbored the highest species richness and relative abundance compared to montane and mossy forest in the higher slopes.

Table 1. Species composition of birds* in Mt. Hamiguitan, Mindanao Isl., Philippines.

Lowland Dipterocarp Forest (75-370 masl)	Montane Forest (371-715 masl)	Mossy Forest (716-1500 masl)
<i>Phapitreron cinereiceps</i>	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	<i>Streptopelia bitorquata</i>
<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	<i>Phapitreron amethystina</i>	<i>Orthotomus nigriceps</i>
<i>Centropus melanops</i>	<i>Macropygia phasianella</i>	<i>Turdus obscurus</i>
<i>Centropus viridis</i>	<i>Ptilinopus occipitalis</i>	<i>Haliastur indus</i>
<i>Cacomantis variolosus</i>	<i>Harpactes ardens</i>	<i>Phapitreron amethystina</i>
<i>Dryocopus javensis</i>	<i>Dendrocopus maculatus</i>	<i>Macropygia phasianella</i>
<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	<i>Hypsipetes philippinus</i>	<i>Ptilinopus occipitalis</i>
<i>Ficedula crypta</i>	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>	<i>Harpactes ardens</i>
<i>Terpsiphone cinnamomea</i>	<i>Zosterops montanus</i>	<i>Dendrocopus maculatus</i>
<i>Rhinomyias ruficauda</i>	<i>Cysticola exilis</i>	<i>Hypsipetes philippinus</i>
<i>Artamus leucorhynchus</i>	<i>Pachycephala philippinensis</i>	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>
<i>Arachnothera clarae</i>	<i>Marcronous striaticeps</i>	<i>Zosterops montanus</i>
<i>Aethopyga shelleyi</i>	<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>	<i>Cysticola exilis</i>
<i>Nectarinia jugularis</i>	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	<i>Pachycephala philippinensis</i>
<i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i>	<i>Pycnonotus urostictus</i>	<i>Marcronous striaticeps</i>
<i>Orthotomus cuculatus</i>	<i>Rhipidura javanica</i>	<i>Loriculus philippensis</i>
<i>Sitta frontalis</i>	<i>Rhipidura nigrocinnamomea</i>	<i>Collocalia troglodytes</i>
<i>Dicaeum australe</i>	<i>Culicicapa helianthea</i>	<i>Rhipidura superciliaris</i>
<i>Corvus macrorhynchus</i>	<i>Aethopyga primigenius</i>	<i>Dicaeum hypoleucum</i>
<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	<i>Ptilocichla mindanensis</i>	<i>Caprimulgus manillensis</i>
<i>Aplonis minor</i>	<i>Sarcops calvus</i>	
<i>Mimizuku gurneyi</i>	<i>Buceros hydrocorax</i>	
<i>Haliastur indus</i>	<i>Penelopides panini</i>	
<i>Phapitreron amethystina</i>		
<i>Macropygia phasianella</i>		
<i>Ptilinopus occipitalis</i>		
<i>Harpactes ardens</i>		
<i>Dendrocopus maculatus</i>		
<i>Hypsipetes philippinus</i>		
<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>		
<i>Zosterops montanus</i>		
<i>Cysticola exilis</i>		
<i>Pachycephala philippinensis</i>		
<i>Marcronous striaticeps</i>		
<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>		
<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>		
<i>Pycnonotus urostictus</i>		
<i>Rhipidura javanica</i>		
<i>Rhipidura nigrocinnamomea</i>		
<i>Culicicapa helianthea</i>		
<i>Aethopyga primigenius</i>		
<i>Ptilocichla mindanensis</i>		
<i>Sarcops calvus</i>		
<i>Buceros hydrocorax</i>		
<i>Penelopides panini</i>		
<i>Loriculus philippensis</i>		
<i>Collocalia troglodytes</i>		
<i>Rhipidura superciliaris</i>		
<i>Dicaeum hypoleucum</i>		
<i>Caprimulgus manillensis</i>		

*Scientific names based from Kennedy et al., 2000 (A Guide to the Birds of the Philippines).

Participatory transect bird survey which listed birds either seen or heard or both but not captured revealed a total of 48 species assigned to 24 families and 10 orders for 472.5 man-hr from all vegetations traversing 18.5 km transect. The length of surveying two km varied in different habitats. Sampling is limited to rugged terrain, steep rocky slopes and weather constraints. Most of these bird species are fruit and seed eaters like pigeons, doves, barbets, bulbuls, mynas, coledo, sunbirds, spiderhunters, flowerpeckers and white eyes similar to bird species composition in the western side of Mindanao (Arances *et al.* 2004).

Using mist-netting method which only include captures, 13 bird species with 28 individuals were trapped for 130 net-days. Majority of these captures were *H. philippinus* (9), followed by *P. urostictus* (4), *R. superciliaris* (3), *M. striaticeps* (2), *C. manillensis* (2), *M. gurneyi* (1), *R. ruficauda* (1), *C. variolosus* (1), *T. obscurus* (1), *M. phasianella* (1), *O. nigriceps* (1), *P. philippensis* (1) and *H. ardens* (1). It was observed that netting success rate is relatively higher in mossy forest

with 23.3% than 21% in lowland dipterocarp forest for an overall netting success rate of 44.3%. Among the captures, *H. philippinus*, *P. urostictus*, *H. ardens*, *P. philippensis* and *M. gurneyi* are geographically restricted to the Philippines. Likewise, *R. superciliaris*, *R. ruficauda*, *O. nigriceps* and *M. striaticeps* are endemic to Mindanao Faunal Region (Figure 3). Non-endemics' existence in lowland forest denotes invasion of these widely distributed species in Mindanao in lower slopes. Threatened species are also high in lowland forest than in upper slopes due to great habitat disturbances receive by avifauna in low elevation. Though bird species inhabit primary forest for the most part in the lowlands up to mossy forest (Baillie & Groombridge 1996), it may be affected by habitat fragmentation. It can be noted that closely related species exhibited overlapping habitats (Miranda *et al.* 1997). Others expand their habitats to higher elevations may be because of their sensitivity to the extent of disturbance in lowland areas. Some of these birds can tolerate various forms of disturbances in the lowlands and that still existed in lower vegetation.

Figure 3. Philippine endemics (a. *Hypsipetes philippinus* b. *Pycnonotus urostictus* c. *Pachypala philippensis* and d. *Harpactes ardens*) and Mindanao endemics (e. *Orthotomus nigriceps* and f. *Rhipidura superciliaris*) captured in a tropical rainforest of Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines.

Species-Effort Curve

The cumulative number of species using line-transect survey method consists of 22 species on July 2006 for 67.5 man-hrs, 30 species on August for 182.5 man-hr, 42 species on September for 241.5 man-hr, 45 species on November for 297.5 man-hr, 46 species on December 2006 to February 2007 for 333.5 and 383.5 man-hr, respectively, and 48 species on March for 472.5 man-hr. Species-effort curve reaches plateau on November and December 2006 and climbed up significantly on March 2007. The increase in number is attributed to the number of sampling efforts provided and more locations explored in Mt. Hamiguitan.

Using mist-netting technique, two species of birds were collected in 40 net-days on August 2006; three other species were collected on September 2006 for 60 net-days, additional two species on December 2006 for 70 net-days and one species on February 2007 and six species on March of the same year for 130 net-days with a total of 13 species. The collection of additional species per sampling as net-days increase indicates that more species may be probably present in the area. This trend suggests that more species are left undiscovered.

Vertical stratification per vegetation type

The preference of bird species in their niche

Figure 4. Vertical stratification of avifauna in a tropical forest of Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines.

utilization may be seen in their occurrence in the different vertical stratum of the forest. As seen in the distribution of avifauna in a tropical forest in Mt. Hamiguitan which coincided with the data of Kennedy *et al.* 2000, there is a discernible pattern of their foraging and roosting sites (**Figure 4**). Ground birds are relatively few than middle storey and upper canopy dwellers.

This significant portion of canopy specialists may be attributed to the well-grown canopy and emergent trees. This is an indication of the canopy utilization of birds like for reproductive activities such as nesting, courtship displays, rearing of offspring; food availability like fruits, flowers, insects and probably predator-free habitat and roosting sites due to the presence of lush branches, vines, leaves and epiphytes. Most birds have narrow stratification while few have broader foraging sites in the vertical forest strata. As a consequence, birds exhibited great specificity or territorialism in a forest stratum. Most of the birds were arboreal than terrestrial. This is supported by the food preference of frugivores and insectivores in mid-storey and upper canopy which also dominated the population of avifauna in the northern region of Mindanao (Jaramillo 2008).

These were observed in captures except those seen and heard during the survey with the predominance of understory specialists such as *H. philippinus*, *P. urostictus*, *R. superciliaris*, *R.*

ruficauda, *M. striaticeps*, *C. variolosus* and *C. manillensis*. The mid-stratum preference of these birds limits their foraging activity on low vegetation like shrubs, grasses and vines. Likewise, netted birds in the upperstory like *M. phasianella*, *T. obscurus*, *H. ardens*, *O. nigriceps* and *P. philippensis* were also abundant. These birds prefer mature standing forest trees when finding food resources for their young during breeding as well as on non-breeding periods. Frugivorous avifauna prefers fruits found on tree tops and undergrowth present in the forest interior (Kennedy *et al.* 2000). General insectivorous birds favor insect population in arboreal strata than on the ground.

In terms of sloping distribution of birds across the increasing slopes with different vegetation, the number of ground, mid-canopy and upper canopy birds occupying the lower slopes is descending as elevation ascends. This signifies sufficiency of food availability for them in lowland dipterocarp forest than in montane and mossy forest in the higher slopes. The carrying capacity of these trees limits avifaunal utilization. Inter-specific and intra-specific competition may arise between them since they consume the same resource supplied by the forest trees. Intrinsic and extrinsic factors are useful for their adaptation. This means that large proportion of forest cover is important for maintaining the balance in the forest ecosystem.

Feeding guilds per vegetation type

Most birds exhibit a wide array of feeding guilds like fruits, insects, nectar, seeds and other prey items. These food resources are found from lowland dipterocarp forest to mossy forest. This study shows that there is a decreasing pattern in the trophic feeding guilds as elevation increases (Figure 5) similar to the previous findings of Silvosa *et al.* (2007). Majority of the bird species were frugivores followed by insectivores, nectarivores, omnivores and carnivores. Frugivores and insectivores chiefly made up the population in lowland forest than in upper vegetations. This is also the same trend that can be observed to the other feeding guilds in the upper elevations. On the other hand, frugivores have the steepest species-area curve and highest species numbers

at dispersion while nectarivores exhibited the reverse (Faaborg 1981).

Most passerines spread out their niches and distributed largely by inter-specific competition rather than by intrinsic factors compared to non-passerines. Generally, passerines are more plastic and more recently speciated (Diamond 1970). Some fruit eaters like bulbuls aid in seed dispersal of fruit-bearing trees as well as control insect pests (Rabor 1986). Most of these forest pigeons and doves are canopy frugivores aggregating as dense feeding flocks with other fruit-feeding birds. On the other hand, the role of insectivores is primarily on pollination of trees with fleshy fruits and small seeds. These are further dispersed by small to medium-sized birds like bulbuls, white-eyes, flowerpeckers, doves, crows and malkohas (Gruezo and Gonzalez 1997).

Endemism per vegetation type

An over-all of 20 (37.7%) and 10 (18.9%) species were found endemic to the Philippines and Mindanao faunal region, respectively. Endemic birds were localized in the forest interior from middle to higher elevations while non-endemics thrive more in lower slopes. As can be seen in the bird's composition (Figure 6), Mindanao endemics consist of lowland dipterocarp forest birds (9) than montane forest (4) and mossy forest (3) dwellers depending on the floral composition documented in their habitats. This shows the

Figure 5. Feeding guilds of avifaunal species in vegetation of increasing slope in a tropical rainforest of Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines.

Figure 6. Decreasing trend of geographically restricted species and non-native avifauna across vegetation in increasing altitudinal range in a tropical rainforest of Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines

decreasing trend of island endemics as elevation increases. Likewise, Philippine endemic species across vegetation show similar pattern in lowland dipterocarp (20), montane (11) and mossy forest (9). This observation conforms to the declining endemism in increasing elevation and habitat in northern regions of the island (Caro 2008). Non-

endemics also achieved the same trend as vegetation changes parallel to altitude. Thus, the regardless of the bird’s endemic status, lowland dipterocarp vegetation nearly doubled the number in upper forest. This finding suggests that except bias in sampling occurred of having sampled lowland forest more frequently than the highly elevated forest in Mt. Hamiguitan; species endemism is relatively high in lowland forest because of the large area covered by dipterocarp trees. Although more Mindanao island endemics were recorded in higher slopes with reduce habitat and anthropogenic activities (Aloy et al. 2007), Mt. Hamiguitan avifauna is able to tolerate initial disturbances of mining explorations, hunting and logging.

Diversity per vegetation type

Shared bird species using Jaccard’s similarity coefficient is relatively higher in close vegetation like lowland dipterocarp forest and montane forest (CCj= 0.44) followed by montane and mossy forest (CCj= 0.39) than in lowland dipterocarp forest and mossy forest (CCj= 0.38) (Figure 7). This is attributed by the proximity of montane and lowland forest than a greater elevational variation among lowland dipterocarp forest and mossy forest.

Some species can only be found in lowland

Fig. 7. Different bird species richness in lowland dipetrocarp forest, montane forest and mossy forest of Mt. Hamiguitan, Mindanao Island, Philippines.

forest which is absent in mossy and montane forest or vice versa. Other species have very narrow habitat range and only utilize available resources in a specific habitat. Some species have wider habitat range than the first mentioned which were documented from lowland forest to montane forest as well as montane and mossy forest only while others exhibit the widest range in lowland and mossy forest. There is a discernible trend of this finding that sedentary birds have narrow niches, low dispersal ability and may have sympatric relationship. Sedentary species may be less affected by habitat alteration than mobile birds which are able to commute from non-forest from their breeding territories to small fragments with enough resources. Moreover, mobile birds have wide dispersal rates, broad niches which reduce competition and live allopatrically.

Moreover, using Simpson's diversity index exclusively for captures, avifauna are highly diversified in mossy forest ($D=5.4$, $E_p=0.9$) than in lowland dipterocarp forest ($D=5.2$, $E_p=0.65$) according to the netting effort which coincided with observations using transect method. This trend in diversity of birds in higher slopes is affected by the degree or extent of forest or habitat disturbance in lowland forest edges as well as competition than to inability to physiologically survive under the physical conditions of the lowlands. Most lowland birds have the ability to move either through jumping, land-bridge crossing, trickling or push-pull shifting to higher elevation. This altitudinal niche shifting is determined by inter-island differences either in altitudinal distribution or in competitive pressure in the lowlands or mountains. Jumping and push-pull shifting mechanisms may be the probable origin of the bird population in higher elevation in Northern Melanesia (*Mayr and Diamond 1976*). However, the effects of forest fragmentation and other forms of habitat disturbance in lowland forest may magnify the reduction in the reproductive success of bird species maybe because of increased nest predation of all species (*Paton 1994 as cited by Sekercioglu et al. 2001*).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The accumulation of bird species in a tropical forest is limited by the altitudinal isolation of

forest vegetation. Vertical stratification, feeding guilds, endemism and diversity of avifauna in Mt. Hamiguitan can be inferred from both vegetation and elevation. Therefore, most of the documented birds are spatially and temporally isolated in areas with potential breeding, foraging and roosting areas concentrated in the remaining forest in different elevations. Mt. Hamiguitan harbors rare, endemic and threatened avifauna. However, continuing operations of logging and mining in their habitats may strongly lead these documented and undiscovered species to local eventually to global extinction.

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